

CHEMISTRY OF BERYLLIUM. PART I. FORMATION OF BERYLLATES

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The formation of calcium, strontium, barium, magnesium, zinc, cobalt and nickel beryllates has been studied at high temperatures and the following compounds have been obtained: $\text{CaO} \cdot 3\text{BeO}$, $2\text{CaO} \cdot 3\text{BeO}$; $\text{SrO} \cdot 3\text{BeO}$, $2\text{SrO} \cdot 3\text{BeO}$, $\text{SrO} \cdot \text{BeO}$; $\text{BaO} \cdot 3\text{BeO}$; $2\text{BaO} \cdot 3\text{BeO}$, $\text{BaO} \cdot \text{BeO}$; $\text{MgO} \cdot 3\text{BeO}$; $\text{ZnO} \cdot 3\text{BeO}$; $\text{CoO} \cdot \text{BeO}$; $\text{NiO} \cdot \text{BeO}$.

Kruss and Morhat (*Annalen*, 1890, 260, 173) obtained $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{BeO}$ and $\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{BeO}$, which on analysis afforded high results for Na and K than what theoretically required. Matignon and Marchal (*Compt. rend.*, 1927, 184, 715) observed that when heated with beryllium metal, MgO and KOH were completely reduced at 1280° and 700° respectively, barium and aluminium oxides were partly reduced at 1230° and 1280° respectively, whilst lime formed a suboxide of calcium at 1230° - 1280° . They further observed (*ibid.*, 1927, 185, 812) that beryllia was reduced to the metallic state when heated in vacuum with excess of lime at about 800° , magnesia at 675° - 690° for three hours, and alumina at 1270° for four hours. When fluxes were used with the reaction mixture containing lime or magnesia, the yield of beryllium increased.

Lang *et al.* (*J. Res. Nat. Bur. Standards*, 1952, 48, 295) studied the phase equilibria of the system $\text{BeO}-\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ at high temperatures and observed the eutectics

- (i) at $1890^\circ \pm 10^\circ$; mol. ratio, 1 BeO : 4 Al_2O_3
- (ii) at $1850^\circ \pm 10^\circ$; mol. ratio, 2 BeO : 3 Al_2O_3
- (iii) at $1835^\circ \pm 10^\circ$; two congruently melting compounds $\text{BeO} \cdot 3 \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ at $1910^\circ \pm 10^\circ$ and $\text{BeO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ at $1870^\circ \pm 10^\circ$.

Preliminary experiments were carried out to prepare beryllates by treating the solutions of sodium or potassium beryllates with solutions of soluble salts of other elements, but in no case a pure compound could be isolated.

The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the formation of beryllates of alkaline earth metals, Zn, Ni and Co at high temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

As acids of different concentrations were used for the extraction of the reaction products, the solubility of BeO , ignited at high temperatures, in acids was studied under different experimental conditions. The results are shown in Table I.

Several mixtures were prepared by weighing out accurately beryllium oxide and the other constituent in different proportions. These were mixed separately in agate pestle and mortar, transferred into fire-clay or graphite crucibles and heated at high temperatures for different intervals of time. Duplicate experiments were carried out in each case and the results reported in the following tables are an average of the two values. The heated mass was taken out, powdered well, and weighed. A known weight of this mixture was taken for analysis. It was washed free of the unchangeable oxides; CaO with 10% glycerine solution and finally with CO₂-free water; SrO and BaO with hot CO₂-free water; ZnO with hot 10% NH₄Cl solution; MgO with 1N-HCl; NiO with 2N-, 5N-HCl and finally with 5% NH₄OH; CoO with 2N- and 5N-HCl. The residue was then extracted with a measured volume of 2N-HCl, 5N-HCl or HCl (conc) and the quantity of beryllium and the other constituents estimated by standard methods in the acid extracts. The chemicals used in the following experiments were of Merck's C.P. quality or B.D.H. Laboratory reagents.

TABLE I

Solubility of heated beryllium oxide at diff. temp. in diff. intervals of time.

Time of heating = 2.0 hours.

Expt. No.	Acid used.	BeO	BeO heated at,	Time.	Temp.	BeO dissolved/100 c.c. of acid.
1	2N-HCl	0.2218 g.	1000°-1050°	5 mins.	25°	0.0032 g.
2	" "	0.2196	" "	1 hr.	"	0.0060
3	5N-HCl	0.2726	" "	5 mins.	"	0.0100
4	" "	0.2950	" "	1 hr.	"	0.0272
5	2N-HCl	0.3152	1100°-1150°	5 mins.	"	0.0012
6	" "	0.3140	" "	1 hr.	"	0.0020
7	5N-HCl	0.2854	" "	5 mins.	"	0.0048
8	" "	0.2806	" "	1 hr.	"	0.0104
9	" "	0.3100	1350°-1400°	2 hrs.	"	0.0000
10	" "	0.3100	" "	12 hrs.	"	0.0284
11	" "	0.2958	" "	1 hr.	100°	0.0456
12	5N-HNO ₃	0.4854	" "	2 hrs.	25°	0.0000
13	" "	0.4854	" "	12 hrs.	"	0.0282
14	" "	0.4714	" "	1 hr.	100°	0.0332

TABLE II

Calcium beryllates.

Time of heating = 2.0 hours. Temp. = 1000°-1050°.

Expt. No.	BeO.	Ca(OH) ₂ .	CaCl ₂ .	Acid (2N-HCl)-soluble CaO.	Compound.
1	0.5 g.	1.5 g.	...	0.2995 g.	2CaO.3BeO
2	"	3.0	...	0.0570	2CaO.3BeO
3	"	4.5	...	0.0502	2CaO.3BeO
4	1.0	3.0	3.0 g.	0.4934	CaO.3BeO
5	1.0	2.0	4.0	0.2255	CaO.3BeO
6	1.0	5.0	10.0	...	...

TABLE III

Strontium beryllates.

Time of heating = 2.0 hours.

Expt. No.	BeO ²	Sr(OH) ₂	Compound added.	Temp.	Acid (2N-HCl)-soluble.		Compound.
					SrO.	BeO.	
7	0.5 g.	6.0 g.	...	1000°-1050°	0.3819 g.	0.2838 g.	SrO. ₃ BeO
8	0.5	6.0	...	1100°-1150°	0.8499	0.3072	2SrO. ₃ BeO
9	0.5	12.0	...	" "	1.8044	0.4370	SrO. ₃ BeO
10	1.0	6.0	SrCl ₂ 6.0 g.	1000°-1050°	1.1152	0.7312	SrO. ₃ BeO
11	1.0	6.0	SrCl ₂ 10.0	" "	0.8052	0.6044	SrO. ₃ BeO
12	0.5	...	Sr(NO ₃) ₂ . 6.0 4H ₂ O	1100°-1150°	1.0288	0.3680	2SrO. ₃ BeO

TABLE IV

Barium beryllates.

Time of heating = 2.0 hours.

Expt. No.	BeO.	Ba(OH) ₂ .	BaCl ₂ .2H ₂ O.	Temp.	Acid (2N-HCl)-soluble.		Compound.
					BaO	BeO	
13	0.5 g.	4.0 g.	...	1000°-1050°	0.3131 g.	0.1524 g.	BaO. ₃ BeO
14	0.5	2.0	...	1100°-1150°	0.4503	0.1129	2BaO. ₃ BeO
15	0.5	4.0	...	" "	1.2178	0.3076	2BaO. ₃ BeO
16	0.5	8.0	...	" "	1.6230	0.3585	2BaO. ₃ BeO
17	0.5	16.0	...	" "	2.3532	0.3872	BaO. ₃ BeO
18	1.0	10.0	10.0 g.	1000°-1050°	1.2436	0.5616	BaO. ₃ BeO
19	1.0	10.0	15.0	" "	1.0245	0.5024	BaO. ₃ BeO

TABLE V

Magnesium, zinc, cobalt and nickel beryllates.

Time of heating = 4 hours.

Expt. No.	BeO.	Compound added.	Temp.	Conc. of HCl.	Acid-soluble.		Compound?	
					Metal oxide.	BeO.		
20	2.00	MgCO ₃	2.00 g.	1350°-1400°	5N	Traces	Traces	...
21	2.00	" "	4.00	" "	"	0.3130 g.	0.6190 g.	MgO. ₃ BeO
22	2.00	" "	8.00	" "	"	0.4780	0.8640	MgO. ₃ BeO
23	2.00	" "	10.00	" "	"	0.7745	1.4554	MgO. ₃ BeO
24	2.00	ZnO	6.00	" "	2N	0.3262	0.3162	ZnO. ₃ BeO
25	2.00	" "	12.00	" "	"	0.4891	0.4758	ZnO. ₃ BeO
26	2.00	" "	20.00	" "	"	0.8343	0.7574	ZnO. ₃ BeO
27	1.00	NiCl ₂	7.00	1000°-1050°	10-12N	2.4255	0.7040	NiO. ₃ BeO
28	1.00	" "	10.00	" "	"	1.9564	0.5632	NiO. ₃ BeO
29	2.00	Co-oxalate	20.00	1350°-1400°	"	3.2460	1.3565	CoO. ₃ BeO
30	2.00	" "	25.00	" "	"	3.8010	1.4558	CoO. ₃ BeO
31	1.00	CoCl ₂	12.00	1000°-1050°	"	2.0712	0.6250	CoO. ₃ BeO
32	1.00	" "	20.00	" "	"	1.9880	0.5520	CoO. ₃ BeO

DISCUSSION

Since BeO is more basic than Al_2O_3 , the beryllates formed in solutions are generally unstable, and $Be(OH)_2$ precipitates out either on dilution or on heating. Some beryllates are, however, formed at high temperatures, and are stable. Some of these are not decomposed even when heated with HCl (conc.).

Calcium, Strontium and Barium Beryllates.

When mixtures containing BeO and hydroxide of calcium, strontium or barium in varying proportions are heated at high temperatures, different beryllates are formed. Their composition depends on the proportion of the constituents in the mixtures and the temperature at which the reaction is carried out.

It is interesting to note that when respective chlorides are added to the mixture, the compound $XO \cdot 3BeO$ ($X = Ca, Sr$ or Ba) is formed in all the cases. The addition of chlorides seems to effect the reaction in two ways: (i) It makes the mass homogeneous and therefore the reaction proceeds to a greater extent than in their absence, and (ii) the reaction, $XCl_2 + BeO = BeCl_2 + XO$, starts at the m.p. of the chlorides, as has already been observed by Booth and Marshall (U.S. Pat. 1392045, 1392046) and $BeCl_2$ formed volatilises away.

In Expts. No. 4, 5 and 6 the quantity of the beryllates formed decreases as the quantity of $CaCl_2$ added is increased so that in Expt. No. 6, when the ratio of $BeO:CaCl_2$ is 1:10, no beryllate is obtained. $CaCl_2$ melts at 780° and considerable time is taken to reach 1000° at which the oxides react to furnish the beryllates. During this period $BeCl_2$ formed keeps on volatilising away, and by the time the furnace attains the temperature of over 1000° , no BeO is left to react with calcium oxide.

Similar results were obtained when $SrCl_2$ and $BaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ were added to the reaction mixtures, though the reaction (ii) was not so marked.

Calcium Beryllates.—It is evident from the Expts. No. 1, 2 and 3 that when mixtures containing BeO and $Ca(OH)_2$ in the ratio of 1:3, 1:6 and 1:9 are heated at 1000° - 1050° , the compound $2CaO \cdot 3BeO$ is formed in all the cases, the quantity of the beryllate formed, however, decreases as the quantity of calcium hydroxide is increased.

Strontium Beryllates.—Expts. No. 7-12 show that strontium forms three beryllates: $SrO \cdot 3BeO$, $2SrO \cdot 3BeO$ and $SrO \cdot BeO$. Mixtures containing BeO and strontium hydroxide in the ratio of 1:12, when heated, afforded $SrO \cdot 3BeO$ at 1000° - 1050° (Expt. No. 7) and $2SrO \cdot 3BeO$ at 1100° - 1150° (Expt. No. 8). This compound was also formed when BeO and strontium nitrate in the ratio of 1:12 were heated together at 1100° - 1150° (Expt. No. 12). It is interesting to note that when mixtures containing BeO and strontium hydroxide in the ratio of 1:24 are heated at 1100° - 1150° , the compound $SrO \cdot BeO$ is obtained.

Barium Beryllates.—Barium also forms three beryllates: $BaO \cdot 3BeO$, $2BaO \cdot 3BeO$ and $BaO \cdot BeO$. In Expts. No. 13, when BeO and barium hydroxide in the ratio 1:8 were

heated together at 1000°-1050°, BaO. $\frac{1}{3}$ BeO was formed. In Expts. No. 14-17, four different mixtures containing BeO and barium hydroxide in the ratio of 1:4, 1:8, 1:16, 1:32 were heated at 1100°-1150°. In the first three cases, a white mass, which disintegrated easily when boiled with water, was obtained. This on analysis has been found to be $\frac{1}{2}$ BaO. $\frac{1}{3}$ BeO. However, in the last case a hard greenish mass was formed which on analysis showed the formation of the compound BaO. BeO.

Magnesium, Zinc, Cobalt and Nickel Beryllates

When mixtures containing varying proportions of MgCO₃ and BeO, ZnO and BeO, NiO and BeO and cobalt oxalate and BeO were heated at 1000°-1050° and 1100°-1150°, no beryllate was formed in any case.

Magnesium Beryllate.—Four different mixtures containing BeO and MgCO₃ in the ratio of 1:1, 1:2, 1:4 and 1:5 were heated at 1350°-1400° for four hours. A very small quantity of the acid-soluble compound was formed in the first case but MgO. $\frac{1}{3}$ BeO was formed in the last three cases. It is interesting to note that the quantity of the beryllate formed increases considerably as the quantity of MgCO₃ is increased. No beryllate was formed at 1000°-1050° on addition of MgCl₂ or K₂SO₄.

Zinc Beryllate.—In Expts. No. 24, 25 and 26, when mixtures containing BeO and ZnO in ratios of 1:3, 1:6 and 1:10 were heated at 1350°-1400°, the compound ZnO. $\frac{1}{3}$ BeO was obtained in each case. When K₂SO₄ was added to the reaction mixture, no beryllate was formed at 1000°-1050°.

Cobalt Beryllate.—In Expt. No. 29 and 30, two mixtures containing BeO and cobalt oxalate in the ratios of 1:10 and 1:12.5 were heated at 1350°-1400°, when a dark blue crystalline mass was obtained. After dissolving the free cobalt oxide in 5*N*-HCl, the residue was boiled with HCl (10-12*N*) several times and filtered. The ratio of cobalt oxide and BeO in the filtrate shows the compound to be CoO. BeO. The residue was fused with Na₂CO₃ and KNO₃ and extracted with HCl. On analysis this also has proved to be CoO.BeO, showing thereby that the total quantity of BeO has been acted upon by CoO.

The compound CoO.BeO is also formed when BeO and cobalt chloride in varying proportions are heated at 1000°-1050°, but the compound formed is a dark blue, amorphous powder in this case.

Nickel Beryllate.—It is interesting to note that NiO and BeO do not react even at 1350°-1400°, but when mixtures containing BeO and nickel chloride in varying proportions are heated at 1000°-1050°, a greenish mass is obtained, which on analysis is found to be the compound NiO.BeO.

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